

Customer Complaint Handling Strategy using the Theory Perspective of Griffin and Michael at PT Maluku Prima Makmur

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Abstract:- to find out the management of complaint handling at PT Maluku Prima Makmur and how the complaint management strategy at PT Maluku Prima Makmur is studied according to the theory of Griffin and Michael and determine the best strategy for making complaint management at PT Maluku Prima Makmur. This research methodology uses qualitative methods by conducting interviews with various key informants at PT. Maluku Prima Makmur. The results of this study indicate that PT Maluku Prima Makmur in handling complaints from consumers must fulfill consumer expectations regarding the failure of the product provided. Replacing products that are not in accordance with the product expected by consumers. Based on the research results, this strategy is the best strategy because it provides compensation to customers with equal value. This was able to create a negative view when making a complaint to return favorably to PT Maluku Prima Makmur.

Keywords:- Strategy, Complaint Handling, Customers, perspective, Griffin Theory, Michael.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to Tjiptono (2000), complaint management is a form of processing, or a contract or arrangement made by the company resolve or overcome objectionable or dissatisfying responses; or Consumer disapproval of the activities of administrative functions Inefficiently and effectively run by the company. Complain.

Customers can and will be triggered by a variety of factors cause customer complaints. Complaint handling is very important because if a company does not respond to customer complaints, consumers will be disappointed and dissatisfied with the company's products. Consumer disappointment can lead to consumer disappearance, negative news spread, and damage to a company's image.

In fact, in order to remain competitive in the consumer market, companies must be able to adequately address various customer complaints. Handling Effective complaints can transform an initially dissatisfied customer into a satisfied customer with your company's products and services, and even into a long-term customer. Results of the study of Pedro et al. (2021) show that the nature of service, the handling of customer-disrupting incidents, and the handling of customer service are key factors in maintaining the producer-consumer relationship.

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In fact, in order to remain competitive in the consumer market, companies must be able to adequately address various customer complaints. Handling Effective complaints can transform an initially dissatisfied customer into a satisfied customer with your company's products and services, and even into a long-term customer. Results of the study of Pedro et al. (2021) show that the nature of service, the handling of customer-disrupting incidents, and the handling of customer service are key.

This is consistent with a study by Salim (2018). It shows that complaint handling has the largest coefficient value that produces customer satisfaction. Based on this research, properly responding to customer complaints can again improve the customer satisfaction index, which in turn can influence and improve the sales of a company's products/services.

All complaints will be submitted to the company and processed It will affect consumer satisfaction and loyalty. A customer survey conducted by the Rockefeller Foundation (Griffin, Customer Loyalty (2005)) states that the reasons for customer loss or attrition are influenced by several factors. (1) unresolved complaints (14%); (2) competitors (9%); transfers (9%); no particular reason (68%).

This research shows that unresolved complaints are one of the factors that influence customer loss. Analyzing the response to customer complaints is therefore an important aspect to consider in keeping your business viable. There are basically three aspects to dealing with customer complaints. customer complaints i.e. aspect (result), result, (procedure) procedure, (Treatment) Treatment Griffin and Michael (2001). in Griffin and Michael's book The title is "Getting Customers Back - How to Get Back and Keep Lost Customers". Them Royal explained that the company did not go through these three stages.

Consumers can then get lost and spread negative news about it. Enterprise in the environment. It's definitely a bad image. For businesses through the eyes of consumers and potential customers.

The outcome aspect is the most expected aspect customer. In this aspect, repair refund or replacement is possible Products/services, cost corrections, or other forms of compensation (Griffin and Michael, 2001). Customers respond negatively when complaints are not resolved, perceiving the company as inadequate or unable to resolve complaints (Tax and Brown, 1998).

The procedural aspect is the aspect that involves actions. Complaints handling is clearly articulated by the company and each step is understood by customers, making it easier for them to file and file complaints (Griffin and Michael, 2001). A study by Tax and Brown (1998) found that the process required by consumers to handle consumer complaints was procedural and expedited, eliminating the need to rotate personnel during complaint handling bottom.

The (Treatment) aspect of consumer treatment is fair interpersonal behavior with customers and showing politeness, concern, and honesty and providing explanations for these failures and trying really hard to solve the problem (Griffin and Michael, 2001). Research by Tax and Brown, (1998) shows that verbal communication is often more suitable for conveying empathy to angry customers than written communication. Consumers don't want to waste time and companies also don't want to waste time dragging on to finish problem, therefore, the faster a solution is found, the more likely the company is to save customers and get very valuable customers.

Customer satisfaction is a post-purchase evaluation, in which the assessment is at least equal to or better than the customer's expectations, whereas customer dissatisfaction occurs when the result is not satisfactory. Losing customers due to complaints that are not handled properly by the company and failure to comply customer expectations are a major frustration on the part of the company. Thus, customer complaints or complaints can be seen as an important indicator for companies to determine the level of customer satisfaction with the products and services provided by the company.

PT Maluku Prima Makmur, is a company engaged in the frozen food industry since 1994. Overall the products produced include Frozen Fish, Frozen Cephalopod, Frozen Surimi, Frozen Shrimp, Value Added, Crab Meat. At this time PT Maluku Prima Makmur has expanded to the Americas and Asia. It is known that one of the basic values applied by PT Maluku Prima Makmur in producing products is quality. PT Maluku Prima Makmur is committed to producing superior and quality products supported by direct handling from upstream to downstream in accordance with the company's commitment to quality.

PT Maluku Prima Makmur has a subsidiary located in the Ambon region, Maluku which focuses on the production of processed tuna products named PT Maluku Prima Makmur. Products made by PT Maluku Prima Makmur are distributed to buyers in America and there are also products that are distributed domestically. Products produced by PT Maluku Prima Makmur are Frozen Tuna, Frozen Tuna Pocket, Frozen Tuna Loin, Frozen Tuna Cube Cut, Frozen Tuna Chunk Meat, Frozen Tuna Ground Meat.

The End User referred to in this case is a consumer who consuming products from Pt Maluku Prima Makmur which are spread in the country and abroad. Every wholesaler who becomes a customer and sells products will deal intensely and consistently with distributors, so that every process of ordering products, administrative processes to complaining about products, wholesalers will convey them directly to distributors and then distributors will forward any problems or complaints to the distributors. PT Maluku Prima Makmur.

Based on the results of initial observations, it can be seen that the number of customer complaints about the quality of products produced by PT Maluku Prima Makmur still fluctuates from year to year. Common complaints given by consumers such as products that do not meet specifications, the presence of biological hazards in them products and various other complaints. Based on customer complaints received and further analysis carried out by PT Maluku Prima Makmur in the 2021 period a total of 17 customer complaints were received. Products that get complaints will be immediately followed up by the internal team of PT Maluku Prima Makmur, Quality Assurance and Quality Control Department by objectively analyzing the product in question, starting from the processing process to transfer to the logistics department. Even though an analysis of the damage and root causes of inappropriate products is obtained, further analysis is needed to find out whether the handling of customer complaints by PT Maluku Prima Makmur is in accordance with the theory of Griffin and Michael so that consumers feel satisfied and do not lose consumers in the business and operational processes carried out by PT. Maluku Prima Makmur, there are special targets set by the Department of Quality Assurance and Quality Control in maintaining product quality and quality, one of which is zero complaint.

Complaints are a natural consequence of every service activity as a result of unavoidable human error. Complaints from customers can provide an opportunity for organizations/companies to identify management problems that they are not aware of. Based on this background, the researcher is interested in conducting research on the effectiveness of handling customer complaints at PT MALUKU PRIMA MAKMUR.

Competition in business that is going strong makes business people always want to attract consumers to be able to conquer the customer market. The high level of business competition is caused by the mindset of a society that is developing due to technological advances and lifestyles that cannot be separated from it the influence of globalization. Therefore this makes the company more persistent in

providing maximum customer satisfaction. However, in practice there are still frequent human errors or production factors. Products that are defective in the manufacturing process or defective so that the product reaches the hands of consumers will result in several negative impacts such as customer dissatisfaction which causes complaints for defective products. If the company does not address these complaints, consumers will be forced to tell their bad experience using the product which is a negative word of mouth that can have a negative impact and reduce company profits. The ever-changing industrial world has a direct impact on increasing competition between companies. Meanwhile, the consumer society began to develop into an increasingly critical society, thus creating a strong high consumer demand for the products and services it produces. Complaint behavior includes at least three forms of response, namely direct complaints by customers to service providers, responses to third parties which are made through negative speech, and personal responses that take legal action directly (Min et al., 2019). Company management's commitment to customer satisfaction in maintaining product quality is one of the main factors in supporting business success. This is because the success of a business depends on consumer judgment, so paying attention to customer satisfaction is very important.

With the number of consumer complaints fluctuating from 2017-2021, PT Maluku Prima Makmur needs to know and understand how to handle customer complaints that need to be done. Based on the research background and previous research that has been done, the formulation. The problems that can be obtained from this research are as follows:

- How is the management of complaint handling at PT Maluku Prima Makmur?
- How is the complaint management strategy at PT Maluku Prima Makmur if studied according to Griffin and Michael's theory?
- How to determine the best strategy for making complaint management at PT Maluku Prima Makmur?

II. LITERATUREREVIEW

A. Complaint Handling

Complaints are a form of consumer dissatisfaction. Complaints have a major impact on the progress of the company. Complaints that are resolved properly and professionally have a positive impact on the company. Customers who complain feel their opinions are highly valued. In addition, complaints are consumers' rights to express dissatisfaction. Complaint or Complaint is part of a negative expression that is generated due to a discrepancy between reality and one's wishes. Consumer Complaint Behavior is a term that includes different consumer actions when they feel dissatisfied with a purchase or service (Sunarto, 2006). Complaint is an action taken by someone, which includes communicating something negative about the product or service that is made or marketed (Oxford pocket dictionary, new edition, 2005).

According to Rusadi (2004), complaints are a sign of consumer dissatisfaction. Complaints should not be underestimated. If ignored, consumers will go unnoticed and eventually leave the company. Complaints need to be responded to quickly so that companies can quickly address the root causes of customer dissatisfaction. In the future, we hope that no one will appeal to the company for the same thing.

B. Customer Relationship Management (CRM)

CRM is the basic paradigm of marketing science that is to satisfy the offender with the best possible alternative in the market through a relationship exchange process. CRM goes beyond transactional exchanges and allows marketers to assess customer feelings and buying intentions so that customers can be provided with goods and services before they ask for them (Panda, 2003).

CRM activity is basically associated with the word relationship. In general, relationship means that you are not buying a broken floor, but there is a relationship that is continuously being built. As is known, before arriving at a buying decision, people will start by searching for information, evaluating the information, and then placing an order. After purchase, the customer may need guidance. Then the next phase is to fix if there is a problem.

The concept of CRM cannot be separated from the concept of relationship marketing. The concept of Relationship Marketing conveys the idea that the main goal of business is a company, namely to invite interaction with customers in the long term (Zikmud et.al, 2003)

C. Customer loyalty

Behavior after purchasing a product is determined by satisfaction or dissatisfaction with a product as the end of the sales process. How is the behavior of customers in making repurchases, how are the attitudes of customers in expressing the products they use and other behaviors that describe customer reactions to the products they have felt.

Every company definitely wants loyal customers because loyal customers will provide long-term benefits for the company. In addition, loyal customers are the ultimate goal of every company.

The definition of customer loyalty by Griffin (2005) is non-random buying behavior expressed from time to time by several decision-making units. This means that loyalty describes the desire of consumers to continue to subscribe in the long term.

III. METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach. Compared to quantitative research, qualitative research has a different orientation and methodology. In addition, these two approaches also have some differences. Ontologically, the quantitative approach sees a single realistic and objective view, while a qualitative view of reality is plural and subjective (Yin, 2011). The quantitative approach places the researcher independent (separate) from the thing being studied, whereas in the qualitative approach the researcher

interacts with the thing he is studying. In qualitative research, researchers try to get as close as possible to the participants being studied. In practice, qualitative researchers conduct research in the "field", namely where the participants live or do activities. The goal is to get the real context and to understand what the informants are saying (Creswell, 2007).

In qualitative research, the thing that must be done at the beginning of the research design is to identify the location and research informants. The research design must determine the location and people who can help the researcher to understand the phenomenon to be studied. This research was conducted at PT Maluku Prima Makmur which is located in the city of Ambon, Maluku province. The informants involved in this study were policy makers and people who received complaints directly from customers.

IV. RESULTS

In this case it can be explained that the handling carried out by PT Maluku Prima Makmur can make services that can be accepted by customers. This is in accordance with what was conveyed by the informants both from the management side of PT Maluku Prima Makmur and from the consumer perspective. It fits with what the informants provided, that the complaints submitted were processed with the existing system and a solution was created to make products or not the occurrence of similar complaints in the future and this made customers feel valued and felt heard so that they still decided to make repeat purchases at PT Maluku Prima Makmur.

A. Correlation with Teroti Michael and Griffin

The handling of customer complaints can basically be viewed from three aspects of customer complaint recovery, namely aspects (outcome) results, (procedure) procedural, (treatment) treatment Griffin and Michael (2001). In Griffin and Michael's book entitled "Customer WinBack-How to Recapture Lost Customers And Keep Them Loyal" explained that when a company does not go through these three stages, consumers will disappear and have the potential to spread negative news about the company to their surroundings. Of course this will be a bad image for the company in the eyes of consumers and potential customers.

Complaints have a tendency to increase product satisfaction and evaluation as long as satisfaction is indeed influenced by complaint intensity (Nyer, 2000). But this is only a case, meaning that this can happen only if the company or management can handle consumer complaints properly and correctly. How complaints can be handled will affect consumer loyalty which gets the relationship between image and complaints on brand trust and customer loyalty.

In the information provided by informants, complaints by consumers are accepted and treated as a medium to enhance customer satisfaction. Later negative effects that will occur if the complaint is not responded to will make the customer leave the company as explained by Griffin and Michael's theory.

B. Aspect (Outcome)

The results (outcome) aspect is the first aspect most expected by customers. This aspect can be in the form of refunds for repairs, replacement of products/services, cost corrections or other forms of compensation (Griffin and Michael, 2001). Customers will give a negative reaction when their complaints do not go away resolved and consider the company inadequate or failed to resolve the complaint (Tax and Brown, 1998).

In this aspect, the result that consumers want for their dissatisfaction is the final product or something that can guarantee an improvement that will ensure that the next product received really changes as expected. On the information provided by the informant, on for export, complaints are always resolved with a commitment to repair according to the buyer's request. This is also in accordance with what is the work guideline at PT Maluku Prima Makmur. Complaints given by consumers become corrections for companies to continue to improve, that way, then consumers feel that the suggestions provided are a reference for change and customers feel happy and continue to be loyal customers to the company.

At the domestic shutter, returns or products are also carried out. The problem was replaced by PT Maluku Prima Makmur, in accordance with what was said by the informant, that any defective product would be brought back to the factory and exchanged for a new one or if there was none then it would be exchanged for the appropriate item. Because the complaints submitted at that time made the same solution mutually beneficial and a benchmark for good service in the eyes of customers.

This is shown by the results of interviews that have been obtained with domestic buyers. "Once a baby skipjack tuna was itchy, I sold it to the women who make smoked fish, then the fish was returned to me because it was itchy. Yes, I complained anyway, I brought the itchy fish to the company, so that it wouldn't be mistaken for a lie, I made it from the consumer, I gave it to the company. At that time I asked for the fish to be replaced according to the amount I brought." This buyer has stated that the goods that had been complained about were replaced by PT Maluku Prima Makmur. In this case, PT Maluku Prima Makmur can do a replacement because itchy fish can no longer be consumed by humans. This is an interesting thing because the buyer explained that all problem goods would be replaced immediately by PT Maluku Prima Makmur. "The company replaces it with the same item, if there isn't one, usually skipjack is replaced by baby tuna, the main thing is the company replaces it with the appropriate item.

The results of the interviews also explained that PT Maluku Prima Makmur did not always replace the problematic goods with the same goods as purchased. There is also momentum for PT Maluku Prima Makmur to replace the damaged goods with other goods that have the same value as described by the buyer.

According to (Tjiptono, 2017) in essence, there is the main purpose of the customer submitting a complaint. To cover economic losses, which are usually manifested by spreading negative news aimed at parties who indirectly also participate in experiences that are not satisfying. That way, consumers can claim compensation legally or through the mass media or directly go to consumer institutions.

In terms of aspects (outcomes), PT Maluku Prima Makmur has provided compensation or compensation that is commensurate with the complaints received which aims to maintain consumer satisfaction. This is also supported by data from PT Maluku Prima Makmur and informants who provide clarity regarding the compensation.

C. Aspect (Procedure)

The procedural (procedure) aspect is an aspect that refers to complaints handling actions that are clearly carried out by the company, in which each stage can be followed by customers and can easily convey or voice complaints (Griffin and Michael, 2001). Tax and Brown's study, (1998) found that the process required by consumers in handling consumer complaints is procedural which is fast and does not change representatives when handling complaints.

In the procedural aspect carried out by PT Maluku Prima Makmur it has been neatly arranged and fulfills all technical matters. From the procedural aspect, it was explained by an informant from PT Maluku Prima Makmur that every complaint was managed properly, and the records were properly recorded and non-conformances were traced to the goods. Not only there, PT Maluku Prima Makmur also conducts various simulations when the worst complaints occur and conducts audits of international standards that are recognized throughout the world. So with this guarantee, PT Maluku Prima Makmur is able to convince consumers that complaints that will occur later will be resolved with the existing systems and procedures that have been recognized by international food certification bodies. The export informant also explained that the handling of complaints was also relatively fast for what was done by PT Maluku Prima Makmur. Not less than 1 day has been able to respond and provide solutions related to existing problems consumer. According to informants from PT Maluku Prima Makmur, all systems are interconnected and neatly arranged, therefore, PT Maluku Prima Makmur is able to guarantee the level of effectiveness and efficiency of the procedures they have implemented.

"Well, when MPM was still M3, they never got complaints, then they got critical complaints related to salmonella, but before that they didn't have a systemized complaint handling system and didn't have global standards, so at that time they immediately went out of business, bro. Even though KML often gets complaints, but because we have a system, we know how to find the problem solving safely. credibility in dealing with consumer related issues. In this explanation, it was also found that the procedure for handling complaints has an important role and must be owned by the company if it wants to continue to grow.

"So from there we know that MPM has implemented a traceability system, so from raw materials to consumers, the products we process can be traced by coding, now that is the main function of the system when there are complaints or complaints from consumers, we can You know where the fish comes from, where the supplier comes from, what date the fish is, what production date, what month, when will it reach the consumer, when will it be exported, we can trace it".

Based on information from informant 3, PT Maluku Prima Makmur already has a system to track products that are a problem. The system is clear and written and tested for its effectiveness in the audit institution. This system has been established and has become a procedural reference for how problem solving is made at PT Maluku Prima Makmur by consumer complaints. This system has been implicated in PT Maluku Prima Makmur, and has also been simulated with each buyer. So, if there is a complaint the next day, then the buyer already knows the system will be implemented by PT Maluku Prima Makmur. "We have a standard for solving problems in less than 1 day. So before 1 day we have to send feedback or an explanation to consumers why complaints like that arise. We also have a mock recall every year which is a system to simulate a customer complaint whether it will later become a shipback or we will simulate a bad possibility, now that's once a year" PT Maluku Prima Sukses is also able to handle complaints less than 24 hours after the complaint given to them. This has also been agreed by all levels and top management. This is also written in the document owned by PT Maluku Prima Makmur when the author validates the document. "if the consumer is still dissatisfied, an audit will usually be carried out, usually there are 2 types, the first audit can be carried out by the buyer, and they will come to our company to check whether the complaint has been repaired or not, whether there is the best solution to the findings That."

In the PT Maluku Prima Makmur reference there is also a reference that if the customer is not satisfied with the services provided or solutions from PT Maluku Prima Makmur. So, an audit is offered from the buyer, you can go directly to the company located in Ambon, or give the responsibility for the audit to a third party at a professional auditing institution. Every year PT Maluku Prima Makmur conducts audits from third parties with the aim of reassuring all their buyers that PT Maluku Prima Makmur has meet global standards from all aspects. Thus making buyers feel more safe and secure.

PT Maluku Prima Makmur also opens time for consumers if they want to make complaints. 24 hours Nonstop management is ready to accept complaints and will provide solutions in less than 24 hours. This guarantee also makes it easier for consumers if they want to complain to PT Maluku Prima Makmur. Media that can be used to complain can also be via email or telephone listed on the product packaging. it also makes it easier for consumers to interact directly without contacting a third party first if they want to make a complaint. This is to avoid negative views on other parties who may not necessarily feel the same experience.

D. Aspect (Treatment)

The (Treatment) aspect of consumer treatment is fair interpersonal behavior with customers and showing politeness, concern, and honesty and providing explanations for these failures and trying really hard to solve the problem (Griffin and Michael, 2001). Research by Tax and Brown, (1998) shows that verbal communication is often more suitable for conveying empathy to angry customers than written communication.

Consumers don't want to waste time and companies also don't want to waste time protracted to solve problems, therefore, the sooner a solution is found, the more likely the company is to save customers and get very valuable customers. "Obviously the problem is said to be solved when the buyer agrees to the solution we provided, Mr. Joko, and of course he will definitely do repeat buying. If the buyer doesn't buy again, it means we have failed to solve the buyer's problem." From the explanation of informant 1, it was said that the standard for resolving cases was when the buyer was willing to accept the solution provided and continue to make repeat purchases in the future. In this case, customers who have complained so far have remained loyal customers of PT Maluku Prima Makmur and routinely buy PT Maluku Prima Makmur products. If the buyer submits a complaint and has been given a solution, but no longer makes a repeat purchase, then it can be said that the existing solution and system has failed.

"There are several factors that make us still take goods at MPM, bro. First, there is the historical factor, bro, because we are also old customers from MPM. Second, complaints are only a small part of the business system, bro, and that happens. only with a small possibility of mass, it doesn't have to be within 1 month that there are complaints, because the fish provided by MPM is sashimi grade fish, of the many containers that we have purchased, only a small percentage of the products are below standard, and the service is also friendly".

Informant 4 explained several factors that made buyers still buy PT Maluku Prima Makmur products even though they had made complaints. The first is the trust factor, this buyer has been doing business with PT Maluku Prima Makmur for a long time, so that trust is also included in the treatment aspect of Griffin and Michael's theory. Second, the informants thought that the complaints were not given every month, because the buyers also knew that the quality of the products sold by PT Maluku Prima Makmur were the best quality fish products. Then the last one is the service factor, the informant stated that the services provided by PT Maluku Prima Makmur make it comfortable and sometimes can provide concessions in payment terms, so that informants feel comfortable. In the treatment aspect, information is given that products that have problems must be resolved and accepted by management with a cool head and still pay attention to customers. The export informants also responded that the services provided when they made complaints remained calm and received complaints properly, when answering and providing solutions they were able to provide peace to the informants. This has also been regulated by systems and procedures that provide services to consumers

must continue to be maintained by anyone.

Domestic informants who asked for compensation also explained that the services provided by PT Maluku Prima Makmur were good and satisfactory. Despite experiencing losses due to providing compensation for defective products, according to management, customers must be satisfied with the products and services provided. This is in accordance with what is in the work guidelines of PT Maluku Prima Makmur.

V. DISCUSSION

The conclusion obtained from the NVivo application which processes data based on the results of interviews with informants is that in handling complaints at PT Maluku Prima Makmur there are 4 instruments where complaints are received, complaints submitted by consumers, SOP for handling complaints and resolution complaint. Then the application of Griffin and Michael's theory to the outcome aspect is alluded to when complaints are submitted by consumers and received by PT Maluku Prima Makmur which means that compensation or compensation has been given when consumers submit complaints. Then on the procedural aspects related to Complaint Handling SOP and settlement of consumer complaints. This can be interpreted that in the aspect of the procedure implemented by PT Maluku Prima Makmur, it explains the SOP that is owned until the complaint is resolved.

Consumers also feel that the complaint problem is resolved by going through several procedures implemented by PT Maluku Prima Makmur. In the treatment aspect, it is found in the complaint handling SOP implemented by PT Maluku Prima Makmur and the resolution of complaints received by consumers. This means that the treatment carried out by PT Maluku Prima Makmur is carried out based on existing and systemized SOPs and also the treatment carried out by PT Maluku Prima Makmur is given to consumers when consumer problems have been resolved.

VI. CONCLUSION

This research is on handling customer complaints implemented by PT Maluku Prima Makmur based on the Customer Winback theory by Griffin and Michael. From triangulation of informant sources and assisted with applications the NVivo 12 data processor obtained the following conclusions:

- PT Maluku Prima Makmur provides a real commitment to make improvements to customers who experience problems with the products received.
- PT Maluku Prima Makmur provides compensation in the form of compensation in the form of a refund or goods equivalent to the product that was damaged.
- PT Maluku Prima Makmur provides vouchers or bonuses for the next purchase because it has helped PT Maluku Prima Makmur find product errors that have been made.
- PT Maluku Prima Makmur continues to apply the existing consumer complaint handling system because the existing system meets international standards for companies engaged in the food sector.

- Complaints are often not detailed and general in nature. Like a bad product, disappointed with quality, or problematic goods. In order for PT Maluku Prima Makmur to understand the actual problem, management needs to ensure the details of the problem by tracing the errors they reveal. The more detailed the root of the problem is known, the easier it will be to provide the best solution for both parties.
- Implementing a 24/7 complaint service procedure where consumers can submit consumer complaints at any time so that consumers do not need to delay submitting problems, so that problems can be immediately analyzed and solutions found for consumers.
- PT Maluku Prima Makmur can provide news to customers regarding progress made, such as replacement products that have been sent or are still being worked on. PT Maluku Prima Makmur can also ask whether the replacement product has been received and whether they are satisfied. Thus, this will minimize the risk of follow-up complaints from customers.
- PT Maluku Prima Makmur continues to provide good treatment to customers who make complaints both when in the process of submitting complaints by customers so that consumers are able to accept the solutions provided.
- Being a better listener to consumers and handling customer complaints also needs to be done with thanks for the complaints expressed. Because the complaints submitted by customers provide information related to the products being sold.
- PT Maluku Prima Makmur in handling complaints from consumers must fulfill the consumer's expectations regarding the failure of the product provided. Replacing products that are not in accordance with the product expected by consumers. Based on the research results, this strategy is the best strategy because it provides compensation to customers with equal value. This was able to create a negative view when making a complaint to return favorably to PT Maluku Prima Makmur.

VII. IMPLICATION

A. Implications

This research has certain implications. Researchers see at least 2 (two) implications, namely academic implications and managerial implications. The academic implications are the contribution of this research to the world of research and the managerial implications are the contributions of this research to the institution under study, namely PT Maluku Prima Makmur.

B. Academic Implications

By conducting this research, the researcher gained insight regarding the handling of complaints that was implemented by PT Maluku Prima Makmur, which had a neat system so that it could be applied at the academic level to support the education system.

C. Managerial Implications

This research is expected to contribute to management, especially the industry, which does not escape consumer complaints. In the interviews it was also found that complaints that were handled properly were able to provide

customer satisfaction and customers felt valued so they did not hesitate to be more loyal to producers.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Creswell, John W. (2007) *Qualitative Inquiry & Research Design Choosing Among Five Approaches*. California: Sage Publication Inc.
- [2.] Creswell, John W. (2012) *Educational Research: Planning, Conducting, and Evaluating Quantitative and Qualitative Research Fourth Edition*. Boston: Pearson.
- [3.] Gilliland, S.W, 1993, The perceived fairness of selection systems an organization justice perspective. *Academy of Management Review*
- [4.] Greenberg, Jerald. (1990). Looking fair versus being fair: managing impressions of organizational justice. *Research in Organizational Behavior*
- [5.] Griffin Jill, Michael. 2001. *Customer WinBack - How to Recapture Lost Customers and Keep Them Loyal*. San Frasco. Willey Company.
- [6.] Griffin, Jill, 2005. *Customer Loyalty: Menumbuhkan dan Mempertahankan Kesetiaan Pelanggan*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- [7.] Hilda Sanjayawati. 2019. Perilaku Komplain, Penanganan Komplain Dan Atribut Hargapengaruhnya Terhadap Kepuasan Pelanggan. *Jurnal Bisnis dan Manajemen*. 6(127-133).
- [8.] Jennifer A Locander, Allyn White, Christopher L. Newman. 2018. Customer responses to frontline employee complaining in retail service environments: The role of perceived impropriety. *Journal of Business Research*.
- [9.] Ke Chen, Jianxun Chen, Wu Zhan, Piyush Sharma. 2020. When in Rome! Complaint contagion effect in multi-actor service ecosystems. *Journal of Business Research*.
- [10.] Long Hoang Le, Quang-An Ha. 2021. Effects of negatif reviews and managerial responses on consumer attitude and subsequent purchase behavior: An experimental design. *Computers in Human Behavior*. 124 (106912).
- [11.] Lovelock, Christopher, Wirtz, J., dan Mussry, J. 2010. *Pemasaran Jasa Manusia, Teknologi, Strategi: Perspektif Indonesia*. Edisi ketujuh, Penerbit Erlangga, Jakarta.
- [12.] Lupiyoadi, Rambat. 2013. *Manajemen Pemasaran Jasa Berbasis Kompetensi (Edisi 3)*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- [13.] Mack, N., C. Woodson, K. M. MacQueen, G. Guest & E. Namey. (2005). *Qualitative Research Methods: A Data Collector's field Guide*. North Carolina: FHI & Usaid.
- [14.] Min K, Jeff Joireman, Hyun Jeong Kim. (2019). Understanding why anger predicts intention to complain among high but not low power customers: A test of competing models. *Journal of Business Research*. 95, 93-102. ISSN 0148-2963.
- [15.] Miquel-Romero, M.J., Frascuet, M., Molla-Descals, A., 2020. The role of the store in managing post purchase complaints for omnichannel shoppers. *J. Bus. Res.* 109, 288–296.

- [16.] Moran Yona, Genadi Birfir, Sigal Kaplan. 2021. Data science and GIS-based system analysis of transit passenger complaints to improve operations and planning. *Transport Policy*. 101(133-144).
- [17.] Nam, K., Baker, J., Ahmad, N., Goo, J., 2020. Determinants of writing positive and negative electronic word-of-mouth: empirical evidence for two types of expectation confirmation. *Decis. Support Syst.* 129, 113168.
- [18.] Nina Yan, Xun Xu, Tingting Tong, Lijia Huang. 2021. Examining consumer complaints from an on-demand service platform. *International Journal of Production Economics*. 237 (108153).
- [19.] Norwell, N. 2005. *Top Tips For Handling Complaint*. London: GP
- [20.] Oliver, R.L. and J.E. Swan. 1989. Consumer Perceptions of Interpersonal Equity and Satisfaction in Transactions: A Field Survey Approach. *Journal of Marketing*, Vol.53.
- [21.] Oliver, R.L., 1980. A cognitive model of the antecedents and consequences of satisfaction decisions. *J. Market. Res.* 17 (4), 460–469.
- [22.] Pedro H. S., Sigal Kaplan, Pastor Willy Gonzales Taco. (2021). Service climate antecedents of transit passenger complaints and temporary opt-out: The case study of Brasília. *Research in Transportation Business & Management*. 2210-5395.
- [23.] Pedro Henrique da Silva, Sigal Kaplan, Pastor Willy Gonzales Taco. 2021. Service climate antecedents of transit passenger complaints and temporary opt-out: The case study of Brasília. *Research in Transportation Business & Management*
- [24.] Poh Theng Loo, Cathryn Khoo-Lattimore, Huey Chern Boo. 2021. How should I respond to a complaining customer? A model of Cognitive-Emotive Behavioral from the perspective of restaurant service employees. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*. 95(102882).
- [25.] Raksmei Sann, Pei-Chun Lai, Shu-Yi Liaw. Online complaining behavior: Does cultural background and hotel class matter?. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*. 43 (80-90).
- [26.] Raval, D., 2020. Whose voice do we hear in the marketplace? Evidence from consumer complaining behavior. *Market. Sci.* 39 (1), 168–187.
- [27.] Ruslan, Rusadi. 2004. *Manajemen Public Relations dan Media Komunikasi*. Jakarta: PT Raja Grafindo Persada.
- [28.] S. Tax and S. Brown, "Recovering and Learning from Service Failures," *Sloan Management Review*, Fall 1998, 40(1), 75-89.
- [29.] Salim A, M. Setiawan, R. Rofiaty, Farid Nur Rohman. (2018). Focusing on Complaints Handling for Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty: The Case of Indonesian Public Banking. *European Research Studies Journal*. 21(3). 404-416
- [30.] Singh, J., 1988. Consumer complaint intentions and behavior: definitional and taxonomical issues. *J. Market.* 52 (1), 93–107.
- [31.] Sophie Jeanpert, Laure Jacquemier-Paquin, Sophie Claye-Puaux. 2021. The Role of Human Interaction in Complaint Handling. *Journal of Retailing and Customer Services* 62(102670).
- [32.] Sunarto. 2006. *Pengantar Manajemen*. Bandung: CV Alfabeta.
- [33.] Thomas Hellbrandt, Ina Heine, Robert H. Schmitt. 2018. Knowledge management framework for complaint knowledge transfer to product development. *Procedia Manufacturing*. 21(173-180).
- [34.] Tjiptono dan G, Chandra. 2007. *Service Quality & Satisfaction*, Yogyakarta: Penerbit Andi.
- [35.] Wujin Chu, Jeongmin Lee, Chris Baumann, Christie Kang. 2020. Fairness perception of ancillary fees: Industry differences and communication strategies. *Journal of Retailing and Customer Services*. 55(102092).
- [36.] Yin, Robert Y. (2011). *Qualitative Research from Start to Finish*. New York: The Guilford Press.